
Good Practice Report

Earthquake forecast communication

Report information	
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What is earthquake forecast communication trying to achieve?

Seismologists work on understanding the movements of the earth and how they might affect the people and built structures on the surface. The information and knowledge that they have, though, is only of use if it helps inform the planning, preparation, and response to earthquakes.

Perhaps the most important, but also the most difficult, questions that seismologists are asked are ‘what is the chance of a damaging earthquake happening in this area, and if it does, what are its likely effects?’ This is the basis for operational earthquake forecasting (OEF), and operational earthquake loss forecasting (OELF), and the answers are always going to have a lot of uncertainty: earthquakes cannot be predicted, however much we know and understand – but we can sometimes tell that they are more likely in certain areas due to movements that have been detected in the earth’s crust.

Forecasts like this require careful, precise, honest and unambiguous communication - sometimes to people who have little or no grounding in the geological principles that underlie the information. They are not warnings, and they are not giving people a ‘message’ – telling them to do or not do something – they are more complex to communicate than that.

This means that the forecasts need to be carefully co-designed with all the different audiences that might use them: an iterative process to understand what information they need to make decisions, their prior knowledge and misperceptions on the topic, and stages of testing how people interpret the information.

What has been done in RISE?

The care method of co-design of communications has been used already, for example, to design “aftershock” forecast communications in New Zealand (e.g. [1–3] and the US (e.g. [4,5], and for multi-hazard communications in Switzerland [6,7].

During the RISE project, we focused on how best to communicate OEF in Europe. We spoke to 173 people in interviews and focus groups, mainly from Italy, Switzerland and Iceland, but including experts based around the world. These ranged from members of the general public to engineers; from storm and flood forecasters to journalists; first responders and civil protection to seismologists.

After several rounds of development of different designs for the forecast information, we also carried out online surveys of 8,196 members of the public across three countries (the U.S., Italy & Switzerland) to measure how they interpreted the risks being presented in the forecasts using various wording styles and graphics.

As a result of all of this work, we have produced a set of guidelines that we hope will help anyone trying to communicate OEF or OELF and have made our test website code freely available.

Before you start communicating OEF/OELF:

1) Be clear about the difference between a forecast and a warning; between information and advice.

This is about understanding the aims of your communication, because you can’t achieve your aims unless you are clear about them in your own mind. A warning aims to change people’s behaviour, through clear advice and messaging – a forecast aims only to give people information which they can use in their own decision-making: there is no advice or message. The two require different communication techniques and would be evaluated very differently.

2) Build relationships with those who might use your forecasts, and those who might help disseminate them

This will help you understand the needs of your audiences so that you can provide them with the information that they want and need, and not just the information that you want to give them or assume that they want. Different audiences might want different things, so you may have to prepare different outputs for them. You may also want to work with audiences to help them know how to respond to the forecast – what actions they may consider. This is particularly advised in schools, but also with others, such as infrastructure managers. When communicating to the public, use the channels that they are already used to using for similar information rather than trying to invent your own: work with journalists in all media, weather forecasters etc. They will also likely know their audiences well and be able to help. Regular meetings with those who are going to try to interpret and disseminate forecasts can also help ensure that any new people are familiar with the format and ready to help their audiences.

When communicating OEF/OELF:

3) Make the purpose of the forecast, and its limitations, clear to the audience

Just as you as a communicator had to decide what the aim of your communication is, so your audience also needs to know this aim. If the audience are expecting a warning with a clear behaviour message, they will be confused and unhappy with a forecast that doesn't give them that. Forecast information can help people make all sorts of decisions, depending on their own circumstances – it is useful even when absolute probabilities are low and there is no official 'advice'. For example, people might choose to practice an evacuation drill, test shut down procedures for power stations, identify diversion routes that avoid tunnels or bridges – all depending on their responsibilities. You're not advising people to do any of those things as part of the forecast, but you can give people a sense of decisions that they or others might make. Making it clear why the forecast is being made public and how it might be of use to some people will help the audience know how to respond to it.

4) Minimise the number of variables that you allow the audience to change

It is tempting to avoid making decisions on behalf of your audiences, and instead to allow every variable to be customised (e.g., the geographical area and time frame of the forecast, the threshold of event size being considered, metrics such as intensity or magnitude). However, if communicating with the public, this is not helpful for most and instead makes the forecast more complex and difficult to understand. Add as little customisation as possible to the main interface: if possible, allow the audience to vary only one thing - the location for which the forecast applies. For more experienced audiences you can allow more customisation via a 'settings' option but work with these audiences to identify the variables they need to change and keep the customisation via settings only to those.

5) Ensure that the forecast is given out regularly & frequently, in the same consistent format, to allow the audience to become familiar with it during quiescent times

People find it increasingly easy to interpret formats as they become familiar with them, so it is useful to expose people to a format frequently. Additionally, familiarity with what 'normal' looks like in terms of the likelihood of a seismic event will help people interpret the likelihoods displayed in times where the risk level is higher and so make sense of it (which it is important that they are able to do).

6) Don't try to communicate forecast information to individuals via a geographical map representation. Only use a geographical map to illustrate the area over which the forecast is valid.

Geographical maps are formats that are very familiar to most audiences, and so they frequently express a liking for information presented in that way. A geographical map can be useful to help them know the area over which a forecast is calculated and valid, but for individuals only interested in the forecast at one particular location, reading absolute risks off a map (illustrated as isolines) seems to be harder than simply displaying the absolute risk probability to them. It may also confuse people into thinking that the isolines on the map represent something other than the likelihood of an event of a set magnitude (e.g. the geographical distribution of intensity of, or damage caused by, a forecasted earthquake, since such maps are often used after an event to illustrate exactly that).

7) Communicate information about what impact people might expect, as well as the likelihood/probability

It's easy to concentrate on communicating the difficult aspect of the numbers involved in the likelihood, but forget that the numbers involved in the impact (e.g. magnitude or intensity) also need to be given a context for people to know what this might mean for them. Although an earthquake of the same magnitude or even intensity can have very different effects depending on the types of buildings in an area, just giving people a sense of what sort of effects different levels of earthquake might have, and in a way that references their experience (e.g. giving examples of earthquakes that they might remember reports from) rather than theoretical (e.g. not through a description like 'light damage likely', which people found unhelpful in our interviews).

8) Present probabilities of events occurring as both percentages (e.g. 'X% chance of an earthquake') and expected frequencies (e.g. 'out of 100,000 towns with exactly the same chance of an earthquake as this one, we would expect an earthquake to happen in X of them.')

People shown a probability as a more solid and imaginable expected frequency perceive that probability to present a higher chance of happening than when shown a percentage. However, such expected frequencies also help people discriminate between low probabilities, which would have several decimal points if shown as a percentage (and where changes of whole orders of magnitude are difficult for people to discriminate). A percentage, though, even with decimal places, is seen as clearer and easier to read, so presenting the absolute risk as a percentage in a big, bold font as the main output seems sensible, whilst also showing the interpretation underneath as an expected frequency. Graphics such as bar charts or icons are not helpful for the low probabilities most often applicable to seismic events.

9) Don't give the baseline risk (the average percentage chance of an event occurring) or a relative risk (how many times higher than average the current risk is) in an attempt to help people understand their current risk level.

Giving context to the absolute risk of a seismic event is important to help people interpret the (otherwise fairly meaningless) probability of such an event. If they have become used to seeing the forecast regularly (see point 5 above) then they may already have an idea of what 'normal' (baseline) is, but the format should not rely on that knowledge. Experiments where people were given the baseline risk in an area as a piece of context to a forecast gave inconsistent results. Where people were given the relative risk between the current and baseline probabilities (e.g. 'twice as high as average') people had a higher perception of the risk (if it was elevated above baseline), but it also seemed to inhibit discrimination between different probabilities. We therefore don't recommend using either a baseline or relative risk as a way to add context to an absolute forecast probability.

10) Allow those who want further context to view a graphic which illustrates the current probability of an event happening in the selected geographical area on a risk ladder, compared with the average probability of the same event happening in a few familiar cities that illustrate a broad range of high to low risk levels.

What does seem to give people useful context to interpret the current probability of a seismic event however, is a graphical comparison of this probability against the average probability in other cities with which they are likely already to have some sense of the likelihood of an earthquake. These cities are likely to be within their country, but may be international in the case of some famously high hazard locations (e.g. Tokyo or Los Angeles). The scale on the risk ladder should be linear, not logarithmic (it can be cut off just above the highest baseline risk). We acknowledge that calculating these comparator risks is complex. Some members of the audience are likely to find the risk ladder ‘too much information’ – especially alongside both the percentage and expected frequency formats described in point 7 - so it is probably better as optional additional information.

11) Allow those who want it to find information about how long events might last for if they happen, and what people might expect in terms of emergency support or communication

Even if you don’t communicate this information as part of your forecast service, work with others who can provide this information to the relevant audiences. People want to know what to expect if an event occurs – how long an aftershock sequence might last, what sort of effects an earthquake might have, how long before things are likely to return to normal, and who has responsibility for different actions.

12) Provide some explanation in normal language, and a personal interpretation service for those who want to be able to talk to a ‘real person’ about the forecast and how to interpret it

Although an automated forecast service might be cost-effective, in order to really support your audiences you should also provide alongside it a short (1-2 sentences) written explanation for the forecast, and a continually-available personal service for those who need to ring to have an explanation of the forecast. It may be worried members of the public, journalists, or key infrastructure managers or political decision-makers – all will need to be supported by a one-to-one service, staffed by people who understand the technicalities of the forecast but are able to communicate about it at any level required. This is no small undertaking, but an important one.

13) Consider ‘prebunking’ misinformation or common misunderstandings without patronising the audience or showing lack of cultural sensitivity

It is helpful to be able to pre-empt potential misunderstandings (such as the difference between a forecast and a prediction, or that large seismic events can happen without warning at any time even in ‘low hazard’ areas). However, it is important to approach this task with humility. Recognise that there is a great deal not known within the geosciences, and that a lot of information is not ‘true’ or ‘false’ but a matter of degree, interpretation or debate. Also recognise that many different cultures have different views on the role of aspects such as fate and that insensitivity to this can easily create barriers between groups and foster mistrust – which can undermine all attempts at communication.

Earthquake forecast
Home Countries Regions Communities
Presets Language

Use the map to select the area you want a forecast for:

Siion-NE (Valais)

Current forecast for a *magnitude 4 or above* earthquake in the area you have selected:

With current levels of seismic activity the chance of an earthquake of magnitude 4 or more happening in this area between
14 Mar 2023 <-> 21 Mar 2023 is:

16%

Imagine **100,000** areas with exactly the same chance of an earthquake as this one.

Within the week of 14 Mar 2023 <-> 21 Mar 2023 with a 16% chance we would expect:

An earthquake of magnitude 4+ to happen in **16000** of them
No earthquake of magnitude 4+ to happen in **84000** of them

[Show me this number in context](#)

Last updated 00:00 14 Mar 2023
Next update due 00:00 15 Mar 2023

What might it be like?

Past examples of magnitude 4 and above earthquakes:

Magnitude

9
8
7
6
5
4
1-3

Not included in forecast

How to survive an earthquake

Click here for useful tips on what to do before, during, and after an earthquake.

Explanation for this forecast:

Siion-NE is seeing higher chances than normal because of increased seismic activity around the Mount Vettore fault system.

[Click here to find out more...](#)

What can I do with this information?

Earthquake forecasts are much less certain than weather forecasts as we cannot see what is happening underground, but they can give useful information to those making decisions.

[Click here to find out more...](#)

Fig.1 Example of the guidelines being tested. See <http://earthquake-forecast.wintoncentre.uk> (source code freely available for use at <https://github.com/WintonCentre/rise-dashboard>).

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